

GEOMORPHOLOGIC MAP OF AMUNDSEN CRATER. L. Wueller¹, H. Hiesinger¹, and C. H. van der Bogert¹, ¹Institut für Planetologie, Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität Münster, Wilhelm-Klemm-Straße 10, 48149 Münster, Germany, (lwueller@uni-muenster.de).

Introduction: Amundsen crater, centered at 84.5°S, 86.6°E, is the southernmost complex crater of its size (~100 km in diameter) on the Moon. Because of its extensive permanently shadowed region (PSR) in the northern part of the crater, its nearly flat crater floor (<7° slope), its vast geological diversity, and its ability to address multiple science objectives [1], Amundsen crater has been proposed several times as a high-priority landing and exploration site [2, 3].

Therefore, we present a geomorphologic map of the Amundsen crater region at a mapping scale of 1:100,000 to provide essential information on the geologic history of Amundsen crater, which is critical for further exploration, landing site selection, and task-oriented mission support, particularly for the Artemis program.

Geomorphologic Map: In our preliminary map, we describe three materials, i.e., basin materials, crater materials, and modified surface materials to illustrate the complex history of the region (Figure 1).

Further Work: For detailed interpretation and enhancement of our map, one of our next steps is to use spectral data and CSFD measurements to further differentiate the plain unit and, thus discuss the origin of the flat crater floor. Furthermore, our goal is to study the PSRs and their potential to trap and preserve volatiles and ice deposits. We will also focus on mission opportunities to sample ancient impact materials, providing valuable insights into the impact history.

In addition, we will perform 1:10,000 scale geomorphic mapping of the Artemis Candidate Landing Site on the Amundsen rim (red box in Figure 1), similar to the efforts of [4]. The combination of mapping efforts at two scales will allow us to interpret the geomorphology and regolith properties of the landing site in a local and a regional context.

References: [1] National Research Council (2007) *Nat. Acad. Press.* [2] Hu et al. (2023) *PSS*, 227, 105623. [3] Lemelin et al. (2014) *PSS*, 101, 149–161. [4] Bernhardt et al. (2022) *Icarus* 379.

